

PRODUCTION OF BORON CARBIDE FIBERS USING BORIC ACID AND CELLULOSE FIBERS

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SUMMARY: This paper presents a route for producing B₄C fibers from cheap and easily available raw materials. Textile cellulosic fibers and boric acid solution are used as raw materials. It is possible to reach an optimal mixture of the primary materials by a suited soaking method. After temperature treatment between 1500°C and 1750°C under argon boron carbide fibers are obtained. The influence of the reaction temperature on boron carbide formation was investigated by IR-spectroscopy, x-ray diffraction, oxygen and carbon analysis. Almost pure boron carbide fibers of good quality were obtained at 1700°C. The shape of the raw fiber is retained during the conversion. The development of the manufacture process is still in progress and an improvement of the strength is expected. The fibers could be an alternative material to commercial available B₄C fibers.

KEYWORDS: production of boron carbide fibers, boron carbide fibers, boron carbide, cellulose fibers, boric acid, organic solvents, soaking method, carbothermic reduction

INTRODUCTION

Boron carbide fibers are very promising ceramic fibers, because they show chemical and physical properties which make them interesting. Low density (2,52 g/cm³), high strength (tensile strength: 2,1-2,5 GPa), high temperature resistance (thermal stability up to 2300°C), oxidation resistance up to 900°C and a high resistance against chemical influences make boron carbide as fiber material attractive [1]. Besides the rigid framework of strong bonded atoms corresponds to a high melting point, great hardness and appreciable electrical conductivity [2]. Boron carbide fibers are actually used for the reinforcement of special materials or inorganic materials which are exposed to highest temperatures and aggressive chemicals. A well known process of B₄C fiber preparation is a chemical conversion of a precursor fiber (CVD-process). Such boron carbide fibers are prepared by reacting of a precursor carbon yarn with a reaction mixture of H₂ and BCl₃ at temperatures around 1800°C [3]. However BCl₃ is a toxic and corrosive gas and additionally hydrogen chloride is generated [4]. The manufacture demands enormous safety care, what leads to high production costs. This paper describes a route which was firstly mentioned in the sixties [5], [6]. In our route we use cheap and easily available raw materials as textile cellulosic fibers (viscose, cotton or wool), which are used as carbon source and boric acid solution serving as boron source. The cellulosic fibers will be soaked with boric acid solution. The infiltrated fibers were treated at temperature ranges between 1500°C and 1750°C under argon. At these temperatures B₄C is formed by carbothermic reduction from boron oxide by carbon. After the conversion the shape of the raw fiber is unchanged.

PREPARATION OF FIBERS

The boric acid is dissolved in water, ethanol, butanol, hexanol or pentanol. Subsequently the cellulosic fibers (Table 1) are dipped in this solution and they soak up the boric acid solution.

Table 1: properties of raw fibers from cellulose

	fiber surface	cross-sectional form	specific surface area	density	fineness yarn
viscose (viscose type)	glossy	serrated	0,1 m ² /g	1,3	330 dtex
wool (wool type)	mat	smooth	0,1 m ² /g	1,3	328 dtex
cotton (cotton type)	glossy	smooth	0,1 m ² /g	1,3	140 dtex

It is possible to reach an optimal mixture of the primary materials and a finally dispersed distribution of boric acid through the fiber material by the soaking method. The molecular ratio of the reactants was calculated from matter amount and molar masses according to the following chemical reaction equation (Eqn. 1):

The necessary mass of boric acid for a complete formation to boron carbide must go to three times of the amount of carbon. Besides the raw fibers are soaked with water with the aim to increase the H₃BO₃ incorporation by swelling the fibers. During the drying process (air drying) the solvent evaporates, but the boric acid remains in the cellulosic frame. After this the infiltrated fibers were heated up to 1560°C, 1600°C and 1700°C under inert conditions in a tube furnace. Further more the heating rate was varied (20 K/min, 10 K/min and 0,3 K/min) and already burned samples were sintered at 1750°C (Table 2). During the annealing the cellulose

Table 2: conditions during annealing of cellulose fibers

	heating rate K/min	temperature °C	dwel time h	cooling rate K/min	sintering	closed crucible
(1)	10	1560	0,1	10		
(2)	10	1600	0,1	10		
(3)	10	1700	0,1	10		
(4)	10	1700	0,1	10		X
(5)	20	1700	0,1	10		X
(6)	0,3	1700	0,1	10		X
(7)	10	1700	0,1	10	1750°C with 20 K/min	X

decomposes into carbon, water and further volatile substances (CO₂ and CO) at temperatures between 240°C and 1000°C [7]. The decomposition of cellulose and the formation of a new structure is connected with a remarkable shrinkage. Simultaneous, the boric acid transforms into boron oxide with lost of water. At temperatures of more than 1400°C a carbothermic reaction occurs and the carbon reduces the boron oxide generating boron carbide and carbon monoxide (Eqn 1). The influence of the reaction temperature, the variation of heating rate and sintering on boron carbide formation were investigated by x-ray diffraction, IR-spectroscopy, carbon and oxygen analysis.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The soak experiments show that the use of water as solvent for boric acid doesn't give satisfying results, because after soaking boric acid crystallize with crystal sizes $\geq 100 \mu\text{m}$ and the distribution of boric acid is inhomogeneous and doesn't adhere on the fiber surface. Furthermore not enough boric acid is absorbed by infiltrated into the fibers for a complete conversion to boron carbide (Fig. 1). The use of organic solvents results in increasing the H_3BO_3 -infiltration in comparison to water. All above, butanol is well suitable as solvent for boric acid, because the H_3BO_3 -infiltration is above 100% of need for all used cellulose fibers. Besides another crystallizing behaviour is observe after drying than in the case of water solvents.

Fig. 1: H_3BO_3 -infiltration soaked cellulose fibers depend on the solvent

The boric acid crystallized finely as a layer around the raw fibers and is homogeneously distributed in them (Fig. 2). Additionally, the cellulose fibers were soaked with water before they were soaked by climbing of the boric acid/ butanol solution. That seems to be the most favourable method. As a result of water swelling the structural chain elements of the cellulose get more distant what leads to an increased cross section. Subsequently more boric acid enters into the fibers. The boric acid dissolved in alcohol get into the cavity of fibers supported through capillarity, and the alcohol promotes the volatilization of the included water, so that the boric acid remains in fine distribution.

Fig. 2: SEM-photo of soaked cellulose fiber with butanol as solvent

After thermal treatment the obtained fibers were investigated by IR-spectroscopy in the wavenumber range between $2000\text{-}500\text{ cm}^{-1}$. In Figure 3 spectra of B_4C fibers of the cotton type are shown. In the IR-spectra B-C bands (around $1090\text{-}1170\text{ cm}^{-1}$) [8], [9] appears, but simultaneously with B-C bands also C-C bands (around $1600\text{-}1585\text{ cm}^{-1}$, $1465\text{-}1430\text{ cm}^{-1}$ and 700 cm^{-1}) appear, what suggest, that aromatic carbon is formed. Fibers annealed at 1560°C

Fig. 3: IR-spectra of B_4C fibers from cotton type and different pyrolysis conditions (c ... closed crucible; lc ... low heating rate ($0,3\text{ K/min}$) and closed crucible; rc ... rapid heating rate (20 K/min) and closed crucible; sc ... sintering at 1750°C and closed crucible)

show intensive C-C bands and only a weak B-C band. But the intensity of the B-C bands grows at higher temperature and after sintering while the C-C vibrations decrease. The increasing intensity of B-C vibrations suggests an increasing crystalline amount. The obtained fibers were also investigated in regard of the carbon and oxygen content by combustions methods. Figure 4 shows the carbon and oxygen content of samples versus the pyrolysis temperature and heating rate. The B_4C fibers still contain free carbon (argement with the IR-vibrations). That results from incomplete conversion of fiber carbon to boron carbide, for instance due to a too low reaction temperature, or it was insufficient boron available due to insufficient soaking with H_3BO_3 . Moreover it is possible that boric acid or boron oxide, respectively, volatilizes during the thermal treatment. This would be connected with a loss of boron. With increasing temperature the free carbon and oxygen content decreases and the boridic carbon content increases. A rapid heating rate and a sintering at $1750^\circ C$ also improve the conversion to boron carbide. The use of closed crucible during heat treatment is also favourable for B_4C formation. The closed crucible prevents the volatilization of boron oxide. The found residual oxygen content can also result from oxide films on the boron carbide surface or incomplete decomposition of cellulose precursor. A good conversion to boron carbide was observed for fibers from viscose type which were sintered. Fibers from wool type with rapid heating rate (20 K/min) and B_4C fibers from cotton type and pyrolysis temperature of $1700^\circ C$ (10 K/min) also showed a good conversion to boron carbide.

Fig. 4: carbon and oxygen content of the obtained B_4C fibers in dependence on the pyrolysis temperature and the raw fiber types: viscose type (v), wool type (w) and cotton type (c); rc ... rapid heating rate (20K/min) and closed crucible; sc ... sintering at $1750^\circ C$ and closed crucible; c ... closed crucible)

Also x-ray investigations were performed to describe the boron carbide formation. As Fig. 5 shows boron carbide is formed after thermal treatment. After a treatment at $1560^\circ C$ first B_4C peaks (marked by "•") occur and in addition carbon related peaks (marked by "x") are observed. The width of peaks and a high underground attributed to amorphous carbon is

characteristic, in particular, of samples of low reaction temperature (1560°C and 1600°C). With higher temperatures the carbon amount decreases and the peaks attributed to B₄C increase. This is characteristic for increase of crystalline phase. Almost complete boron carbide formation, according to the x-ray pattern, is obtained at 1700°C.

Fig. 5: x-ray patterns of produced B₄C fibers (a) cotton type/1560°C; (b) cotton type/1700°C; (c) viscose type/1600°C; (d) viscose type/1700°C

The surface area of fibers was measured by BET and the results are shown in Fig. 6. High specific surface areas of up to 16 m²/g were found. B₄C fibers of the cotton type show high specific surface areas at temperatures of 1700°C and heating rates of 20 K/min, 10 K/min and 0,3 K/min. But the surface area goes to a lower value after sintering. The fibers with wool

type show only a high specific surface area ($14 \text{ m}^2/\text{g}$) if a high heating rate was used. Only B_4C fibers from viscose type show a high specific surface area after sintering in contrast to the others. An increasing surface area indicates crystallization of fibers, which results in growth of grains and pores. The reason for coarsening is apparently surface-to-surface mass transport owing to gas formation during pyrolysis [10]. During pyrolysis volatile gases (for instance CO , CO_2 , volatile boron oxide) occur due to decomposition of the raw materials and as a product of carbothermic reduction. The weight loss of the fibers after temperature treatment was rather high (around 90%). Coarsening effects were also found by SEM investigations. The specific surface area obviously depends on the heating rate and the occurring gas forming reactions.

Fig. 6: specific surface area of B_4C fibers from different raw fibers and varied pyrolysis conditions (rc ... rapid heating rate (20K/min) and closed crucible; lc ... low heating rate (0,3 K/min); sc ... sintering at 1750°C and closed crucible)

SEM investigations from obtained fibers with viscose and cotton as raw fibers are shown in Figures 7 and 8. B_4C is found as main component and the shape of the raw fiber is unchanged. The surface of B_4C fibers from cotton type is smooth and fairly dense (Fig. 7). But the B_4C fibers from viscose type (Fig. 8) show submicrometer particles of relative uniform size ($\leq 1\mu\text{m}$), which are interconnected. The fibers indicate coarsening without of densification. This is a consequence of mass- transport processes, for instance by surface and vapor-phase diffusion processes [10]. However B_4C fibers as viscose raw material, sintered at 1750°C or fired at 1700°C with rapid heating rate show less tendency of coarsening.

Fig. 7: SEM-photo of B_4C fibers from cotton type and a pyrolysis temperature of $1700^\circ C$

Fig. 8: SEM micrograph of B_4C fibers from viscose as raw fiber and a pyrolysis temperature of $1700^\circ C$

The coarsening of the fibergrains during pyrolysis is unfavourable regarding mechanical properties and corrosion resistance of fibers.

CONCLUSIONS

The preparation of B_4C fibers from fibers cheap and easily available materials boric acid and cellulose is simple and ecological method. Such fibers can be an alternative to commercial B_4C fibers for special applications. A good infiltration of cellulose fibers with boric acid is obtained, if butanol is used as solvent. The combination firstly water swelling and following butanol soaks is a favourable infiltration method. The investigations after temperature treatment show that boron carbide occurs at above $1500^\circ C$. But the obtained fibers still contain free carbon, whose content decreases with increasing temperature up to $1700^\circ C$ and

by sintering at 1750°C. A complete conversion to boron carbide occurs if sufficient boric acid was infiltrated. A preparation problem results from microstructural coarsening during temperature treatment. Such behavior makes the mechanical properties drop down. The effect of coarsening can be inhibited by sintering additives during pyrolysis. The idea of these additives is to activate grain boundary diffusion and volume diffusion or to inhibit surface diffusion. An improvement of strength will be still in development.

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